

Phenoxide and Naphthoxide Derivatives of Diarylthallium(III) Cation

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THE interaction of dialkylthallium(III) compounds with some substituted phenols is known¹ and a few substituted phenoxide have also been isolated in the crystalline state and characterised^{1,2}. In continuation to our studies on diorganothalliums³⁻⁵ now we report the synthesis and characterisation of some diarylthallium(III) phenoxide and naphthoxide (aryl = phenyl, *o*-tolyl *m*-tolyl or *p*-tolyl). The conductometric and I.R. data of the compounds respectively, indicate very feeble ionisation in the solution and a Tl-O bond with insignificant $p\pi-d\pi$ bonding.

Experimental

Diarylthallium(III) derivatives were prepared according to literature methods^{7,8}. Other reagents of analytical grade (BDH/S. Merk) were used without further purification but freshly distilled dimethylformamide was employed in the conductometry.

In a typical preparation, 1 m mole of diarylthallium(III) chloride in 50 ml of pyridine-water mixture (1:1) was treated with a concentrated aqueous solution of excess of sodium phenoxide or β -naphthoxide (5 m mole) and the mixture was stirred 4-5 hours on a water bath. The precipitated diarylthallium(III) phenoxide or β -naphthoxide was filtered, washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried at 90° (yield 70-90%). The experimental data are collected in the Table.

The compounds are thermally stable at room temperature but decompose when heated to their melting points. These pale yellow to dirty green crystalline solids are insensitive to atmospheric moisture and oxygen, insoluble in common organic solvents such as benzene, chloroform, diethyl-ether, etc. but dissolve appreciably in pyridine, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide.

Elemental analyses were done at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow with certain modifications but thallium was estimated as Tl_2CrO_4 from $H_2SO_4-HNO_3$ digested samples⁹.

The infrared spectra of the compounds in nujol were recorded in the region of 4000-200 cm^{-1} using Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer model 521. The calibration was performed with a polystyrene film. The accuracy is thought to be $\pm 4 cm^{-1}$. The melting points of the compounds were determined on electrically operated apparatus, M/s. Toshniwal and Brothers, Bombay, India. Molar conductance of $10^{-3}M$ solutions measured in dimethylformamide using a Phillips conductivity bridge type PR 9500 having a dip type conductivity cell at 30°, was found to be in the range of 2.4-4.3 $ohm^{-1} cm^2 mole^{-1}$ indicating very feeble ionisation of the compounds in solution. Due to insolubility of the compounds in suitable solvents, molecular weight could not be determined either cryoscopically or by the Rast method. This poses restrictions in understanding the degree of polymerisation and to correlate structure with the known compounds.

Various infrared absorptions associated with aromatic group are observed at the positions reported in one of our earlier publications⁶, are not listed here. The absorptions associated with asymmetric C-O and symmetric C-O along with Tl-O are summarised in the last column of the Table.

Butcher *et al*¹⁰ examined the spectra of various

TABLE I—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR DIARYLTHALLIUM(III) PHENOXIDE AND NAPHTHOXIDE

Compound	m.p. °C	Analytical data, found (calcd.) % element			I.R absorption bands		
		Tl	C	H	$\nu_{asym} C-O$	$\nu_{sym} C-O$	ν_{Tl-O}
$(C_6H_5)_2TlOC_6H_5$	233-34 d	45.4 (45.5)	47.9 (47.8)	3.3 (3.3)	1077 m	1023 s	306 vw
$(o-CH_3C_6H_4)_2TlOC_6H_5$	210 d	42.7 (42.5)	49.9 (50.1)	4.3 (3.9)	1076 m	1034 m	315 w
$(m-CH_3C_6H_4)_2TlOC_6H_5$	212 d	42.5 (42.5)	49.9 (50.1)	3.9 (3.9)	1077 w	1025 w	310 w
$(p-CH_3C_6H_4)_2TlOC_6H_5$	230-83 d	43.0 (42.5)	50.4 (50.1)	4.2 (3.9)	1072 m	1020 m	305 w
$(C_6H_5)_2TlOC_{10}H_7$	210-12 d	40.2 (40.5)	52.2 (52.4)	3.2 (3.3)	1060 m 1070 m	1020 m	312 w
$(o-CH_3C_6H_4)_2TlOC_{10}H_7$	205 d	38.2 (38.5)	54.6 (54.4)	4.2 (4.0)	—	1030 m	314 m
$(m-CH_3C_6H_4)_2TlOC_{10}H_7$	208 d	38.5 (38.5)	54.3 (54.4)	4.2 (4.0)	1070 vw	1020 w	308 vw
$(p-CH_3C_6H_4)_2TlOC_{10}H_7$	240 d	38.0 (38.5)	54.5 (54.4)	4.2 (4.0)	1073 m	1016 s	314 m

d = decomposition, m = medium, s = strong, v = very and w = weak.

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dialkyltin dialkoxides and pointed out that remarkably high intensity of the C—O bands in these compounds is due to $p_{\pi}-d_{\pi}$ bonding between the oxygen and tin atoms. The intensity of this absorption in the present investigation is usually weak to medium, which may be due to insignificant $p_{\pi}-d_{\pi}$ bonding between the oxygen and thallium atoms on account of the electron withdrawing effect of phenyl and naphthyl group in these compounds. Tl—O stretching vibration in the compounds appears at 310 ± 5 which is close to the reported value for dialkylthallium alkoxides¹¹.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium with 2 : 2'-bis (2-pyridyl)-benzothiazole and 2 : 2'-bis(o-mercaptophenyl)-acetylacetonato anil

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC determination and stability constants of the complexes of osmium with 2 : 2'-bis(2-pyridyl)-benzothiazole (Reagent I) and

2 : 2'-bis(o-mercaptophenyl)-acetylacetonato anil (Reagent II) respectively, have been made. The maximal absorption being 490 nm and 480 nm for reagents I and II, at 0.50 to 3.0M and 0.10 to 2.0M HCl medium, whereas sensitivities are $0.0200 \mu \text{ g cm}^{-2}$ and $0.0250 \mu \text{ g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The optimal ranges for Beer's law are 4 to 16 ppm and 4 to 12 ppm for reagents I and II, the per cent. relative analysis errors being 2.60 and 2.74 respectively, whereas molar extinction coefficient values are $1.0 \times 10^4 \text{ mole cm}^{-1}$ and $7.25 \times 10^3 \text{ mole cm}^{-1}$. Composition of the complexes are evaluated and stability constants were calculated by the Leden's and Rosenstein's methods, which agree quite well.

Organic reagents having N, O or S donor atoms have been described for spectrophotometric determination of osmium^{1,2}. They offer varied nature of sensitivity and selectivity under experimental conditions. Chelating agents containing C—S bridge or S—S bridge have a tendency to give coloured complexes with osmium. Sulphur can take part in M→L back π -bonding causing therein high stability. In this present paper, spectrophotometric determination of osmium and evaluation of stability constants have been described with reagents like benzothiazole containing C—S bridge and a Schiff's base anil containing S—S bridge. Both the reagents give red or red-violet coloured complexes with osmium and are suitable for spectrophotometric determination. The systems of osmium complexes are sensitive, follow Beer's law over a considerable range. The stability constants of the complexes were evaluated by a few standard methods where they agree quite well.

Reagents, Apparatus and Solutions

Preparation of 2 : 2'-bis(2-pyridyl)-benzothiazole [Reagent-I]

2 : 2'-bis pyridyl ketone (A.R. grade) and 2-amino thiophenol (Fluka) in 1 : 1 mole ratio was refluxed in absolute alcohol for 6 hours. The reaction mixture on cooling gave pale yellow crystals. The product was recrystallised from absolute ethanol to give white needle-shaped crystals. Yield—40% m.p. 132°. On analysis : found, 69.79% C, 4.36% H, and 14.30% N, Calc. for $C_{17}H_{13}N_3S$, 70.00% C, 4.47% H and 14.43% N.

2 : 2'-bis(o-mercaptophenyl)-acetyl acetonato anil (a Schiff's base) [Reagent-II].

Acetyl acetone (BDH) 10 g and 2-amino-thiophenol (Fluka) 25 g were refluxed in benzene medium in presence of 25 ml of freshly distilled pyridine for 6 hours when a deep orange mixture was obtained. On cooling at room temperature for 2 days, orange crystals separated out which was washed with ligroin and dried in vacuum.

Yield—2.5 g ; m.p. 184°